

Original Research Report

Acceptability of Suitably Designed Garments for Nursing Mothers in Ondo City Metropolis, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study was designed to compare the appropriateness of the usual and suitably designed garments for nursing mothers in Ondo City metropolis. The study adopted descriptive survey design and research and development (R&D) methods. Three hundred and sixty (360) respondents were randomly selected from nine immunization clinic centers in Ondo City Metropolis. Two research questions and one null hypotheses (tested at 0.05 level of significance) guided the study. Specifically the study sought to document the challenges encountered by nursing mothers in using the usual garments for breastfeeding, and to identify features of an appropriate garment that can be suitably designed for breastfeeding. The instrument used for data collection was Breast-Feeding Mothers Opinion Questionnaire. The data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that nursing mothers encounter challenges in using the usual garments for breastfeeding. These challenges include, but are not limited to, unavailability of the desired design for nursing garments, inappropriate time or place to express breastfeeding, inability to understand figure type and faults so as to choose suitable and flattering styles, inability to find nursing garments that fit to the desired design, among others. The study also found out garments that are good for breastfeeding. It was recommended that dress makers take a proactive stance to produce comfortable, convenient and beautiful designs for nursing mothers.

Keywords: Appropriateness, Breast Feeding, Convenience, Garments, Nursing Mothers

1. Introduction

Breastfeeding is the act of feeding baby with breast milk to enhance adequate growth and development. World Health Organization (WHO, 2019) defined breastfeeding as the normal way of feeding babies with nutrients needed for a healthy growth and development, while nursing mother is a woman who is breastfeeding her baby with her own breast milk. Breastfeeding has received much international attention in the maternal-child health in the past few decades due to its numerous benefits to mothers and child. The importance of breast milk cannot be over-emphasized as it promotes the sensory and mental development of the child as well as the prevention of contagious, infectious and chronic diseases. Riordan and Wambach (2010) opined that breastfeeding protects babies in the first three years of infant life from gastrointestinal, respiratory, ear and urinary tract infections. Babies stand to benefit in several ways if adequately breastfed at the appropriate time.

Another worry is that, majority of nursing mothers find breastfeeding in public difficult because of the culture of sexualization associated to exposure of breast in public. Nursing mothers have to raise their gowns or blouse in order to have access to their breast for breastfeeding which in turn exposes their breast, back and tummy. Exposure of female breast during breastfeeding in the public appears inappropriate and immoral to some persons and even embarrassing to others. Again, exposure of breast may be seen as a symbol of carnal desire, sex and lust to some persons. Breastfeeding is an obligation for nursing mothers but must be used without exposure in public. Jamil (2015) reported that many nursing mothers who return to work after the usually short-lived maternity leave always give up breastfeeding completely or partially because of unavailability of time or place to express breast.

The cultural environment of the western society does not encourage breastfeeding of babies in the public places because of the humiliation associated with it, which makes nursing mothers to look for a substitute to breastfeeding. Against this backdrop, Smith (in Alidu, 2016) opines that breastfeeding is not an excretory function and baby should not be hidden when breastfeeding. In August 2018, the world celebrated World Breastfeeding Week in which the World Health Assembly embraced the annual celebration as an estimable way to encourage support for the protection and promotion of breastfeeding everywhere. Notwithstanding, a means of ensuring the convenience of the nursing mother is crucial. The provision of suitable garments that can serve several other functions while allowing for ease in breastfeeding is unavoidable.

Nursing mothers within the age range of 20-35 years, due to their status such as education, finance, job among others are not always comfortable breastfeeding in public places due to the kind of garment worn. Alidu (2016) observed that some nursing mothers had to raise up their blouses in order to bring out their breast for breastfeeding. It is a common thing in and around Ondo City metropolis to see young mothers always going about with either handkerchief or a shawl to cover their breast while breastfeeding or at times tie the shawl on the waist to pull their gowns to conveniently breastfeed both in the creche, workplace or while visiting people which is not so ideal and most importantly not comfortable for both the mother and the baby; this practice seems to be common among the educated nursing mothers.

Due to the contribution of women to the socio-economic development of the nations in recent times and the need for engaged nursing mothers to fulfill the required recommendations of World Health Organization (WHO, 2017), and the International Baby Food Action Network (IBFAN, 2018) for exclusive and adequate breastfeeding of infants, the need of nursing garments for nursing mothers for easy access to breastfeeding without body exposure is expedient. This study is therefore

poised to analyze the production and acceptability of suitably designed garments for nursing mothers in Ondo City Metropolis.

The findings of this study would be of utmost importance to breastfeeding mothers in Ondo metropolis who would be able to engage in breastfeeding anywhere and anytime without limitation. The acceptability of suitable nursing garments will also be of benefit to the employer as nursing mothers will concentrate more on their job. The findings of this study also, will create market and job opportunities for youths and fashion designers as it will serve as source of income to them. Also, nursing mothers in Ondo metropolis would be made aware of ideal nursing mother garments that would be useful after weaning as this will allay the fear of wasted clothes and money. Moreover, this study will serve as a basis for further research.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Studies have shown that most nursing mothers who return to work after child delivery resort to using infant formula in feeding their babies too early even before they reach the age of six (6) months as against WHO & UNICEF recommendation of six months exclusive breastfeeding for the prevention of diseases. Babies are therefore deprived of breast milk as a result of the nature of their mother's job. The major problem is that, most nursing mothers deny their babies of breast milk because they lack a good understanding of the best nursing garments suitable for nursing and also the nature of nursing mothers job dictates the kind of cloth she wears to the work place and the these dresses they wear most time may not give room for easy accessibility to breastfeeding anytime and anywhere.

Another worry is that, nursing mothers find it challenging to breast feed in the public because of the culture of sexualization associated to exposure of breast in public. Nursing mothers have to lift up their gowns or blouse in an attempt to access their breast for breastfeeding which expose the breast back and tummy and some persons perceive this as immoral, inappropriate and embarrassing.

Due to need for nursing mothers to fulfill the required recommendation of the World Health Organization (WHO) (2017) for exclusive and adequate breastfeeding of infants; the need to identify challenges faced by nursing mothers and features of an appropriate garment design for breastfeeding is therefore expedient.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study is to compare the appropriateness of the usual and suitably designed garments for nursing mothers in Ondo City metropolis. Specifically, the study:

- (a) examined the challenges encountered by nursing mothers in using the usual garments for breastfeeding, and
- (b) identified features of an appropriate garment design for breastfeeding.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for the study:

- (a) What are the challenges encountered by nursing mothers in using the usual garments for breastfeeding?
- (b) What are the features of an appropriate garment design for breastfeeding?

1.4. Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of young and old nursing mothers on challenges encountered by in using the usual garments for breastfeeding.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study employed descriptive survey research design. It is suitable for this study as it aims at eliciting information from the respondents (nursing mothers) on their opinions on the challenges encountered with the use of usual and suitably designed garments for convenient breastfeeding.

Table 1: Population Distribution of Nursing Mothers in Ondo City metropolis

S/N	Immunization Clinics Centre	Numbers of nursing mothers
1	General Hospital, Ondo	56
2	Basic Health Centre, Jilalu, Ondo	128
3	Basic Health Centre, Better Life, Ondo	212
4	Mother and Child	55
5	Basic Health Centre, Ayeyemi, Ondo	102
6	Basic Health Centre, Oka, Ondo	68
7	Basic Health Centre, Yaba, Ondo	145
8	Basic Health Centre, Sabo Oja, Ondo	53
9	Basic Health Centre, Surulere, Ondo	70
	Total	889

Source: *Information and Data Unit (Better Life, 2019)*

Nine (9) immunization centres were randomly selected from the twelve (12) immunization centres using simple random technique. Forty nursing mothers were randomly selected from each of the selected centres. The total sample size selected was three hundred and sixty (360) respondents.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

This research reflects the authors research and analysis and it is not been considered for publication elsewhere. The researchers informed the respondents about the research and the purpose of the study. Verbal informed consent was obtained from officials of the immunization clinics to allow the survey to be carried out in their units; verbal informed consent was also obtained from nursing mothers for their participation in this study; for their responses to be published in this article and their anonymity was assured by the researchers

2.2. Area of the Study

Ondo State, generally referred to as the “Sunshine State”, was created from the defunct Western Region on 3rd February, 1976. Before its creation, the state existed as the Ondo Province of the Old Western Region. The State covers a land area of 14,973 square kilometer. The population of the State as revealed by the Year 2006 population is 3,441,024. The State consists of Eighteen Local Government Areas and blessed with a rich ethnic composition largely from the Yoruba subgroups of the Akoko, Akure, Ikale, Ilaje, Ondo and Owo people. Ijaw minority such as Apoi and Arogbo and Ilaje populations inhabit the coastal areas. Ondo state is located in the Southwester geopolitical zone of Nigeria and bounded by the North by Ekiti and Kogi States, in the East by Edo State, in the west by Osun and Ogun States and in the south by the Atlantic Oceans. Ondo State is located entirely within the tropics (www.ondostate.gov.org).

2.3. Population and Sample

The population of the study consisted of 889 nursing mothers at the immunization clinics in Ondo City metropolis. They are Jimkun, Surulere, Ayeyemi, Yaba, Mofere Market, Maroko, Oka, Jilalu, Sabo Oja, Mother and Child and Better life. The comprehensive data on the number of breastfeeding mothers according to the immunization centres are shown in the table below:

2.4. Data Collection Technique

Data collection was done with a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire, titled “Breast Feeding Mothers Opinion Questionnaire” (BFMOQ), was based on the research questions and the literature reviewed. It was divided into two sections. Section A is about the demographic information of the respondents, while section B consisted of questionnaire items in line with the research questions. Respondents responded to each questionnaire item following a four point Likert-scale. The instrument was face and content validated by experts in the University of Benin, Benin City. To measure the reliability of the instrument, split-half coefficient of consistency (stability) was calculated from the response of 30 respondents outside the area of study. A value of 0.78 was obtained which signified that the reliability of the instrument is high.

2.5. Data Analysis Technique

The questionnaires were administered to 360 nursing mothers in Ondo City metropolis. 358 copies of the questionnaire were however retrieved. Data collected from the respondents were statistically analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used for descriptive analysis. A cut-off point (COP) of 2.50 was used to determine acceptability or rejection of items. The null hypothesis was tested with t-test analysis at 0.05 level of significance. If the P-value is greater than 0.05, the difference in the mean responses of young and old nursing mothers was considered as insignificant, otherwise it was considered significant.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* What are the challenges encountered by nursing mothers in using the usual garments for breastfeeding?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the challenges encountered by nursing mothers using usual garment for breastfeeding

S/N	Item	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Unavailability of the desired design for nursing mothers	2.74	1.187	Agreed
2	Inappropriate dress for the right occasion and custom of the land is a challenge	2.46	1.131	Disagreed
3	Most nursing mothers who return to work give up breastfeeding partially or completely because they do not have appropriate time or place to express breastfeeding	2.59	1.078	Agreed
4	Inability to understand figure type and faults so as to choose suitable and flattering styles	2.53	1.052	Agreed
5	High cost of clothing articles	2.36	1.113	Disagreed

6	Inability to find nursing garments that fit to the desired design	2.54	1.138	Agreed
7	Inability of a designer to sew and suit the taste of nursing mothers	2.51	1.183	Agreed
8	Use of free hand cutting may result to garment not fitting on the body	2.34	1.210	Disagreed

Key: \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard deviation

Source: *Field Survey (2019)*

Table 1 depicts that the respondents rated all the eight items as agreed with an aggregate mean rating ranging from 2.34 to 2.74 and aggregate standard deviation ranging from 1.052 to 1.210. With these results, the above mean score shows that the respondents agreed to five of the items suggested as the challenges encountered by nursing mothers in using usual garments for breastfeeding, while they disagreed to three.

Breastfeeding poses many challenges to nursing mothers especially when they have to use their usual garments. In answer to the first research question, there are some garment-related challenges nursing mothers experience while trying to breastfeed their children. Such challenges include unavailability of the desired design for nursing garments, inappropriate time and place to express breastfeeding, inability to understand figure type and faults to choose suitable and fitting style, inability to find nursing garments that fit to the desired design, and inability of designers to sew and suit the taste of nursing mothers. As observed, these challenges are often as a result of how their garments are constructed and designed. In line with these findings, Jamil (2015) reported that many nursing mothers who return to work always give up breastfeeding completely or partially because of unavailability of time, or place to express breastfeeding. Similarly, the finding is also in support of that of Alidu (2016), that the burdensome and inconveniences of uneasy access to the breast cause many nursing women not to breastfeed their babies at the appropriate time in order to meet the breast milk demand by their babies as and when due.

3.2. *Research question two:* What are the features of an appropriate garment design for breastfeeding?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the features of an appropriate garment design for breastfeeding

S/N	Item	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Garment with inconspicuous zippers at the princess lines at the centre front	3.72	0.591	Agreed
2	Garment with a form of closure at the under bust (CF) using snaps	3.52	0.664	Agreed
3	Garment with a form of closure using inconspicuous fastening at bust	3.61	0.633	Agreed

4	Garment with flap covering fastening the layer of dress	3.44	0.636	Agreed
5	Garment with concealed opening at invited pockets at bust regions	3.58	0.651	Agreed
6	Garment with a form of closure using zipper in the centre	3.55	0.667	Agreed

Key: \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard deviation

Source: *Field Survey (2019)*

Table 2 reveals that the respondents rated all the six items as agreed with an aggregate mean rating ranging from 3.44 to 3.72 and aggregate standard deviation ranging from 0.591 to 0.667. With these results, the above mean score shows that the respondents agreed that garment designs with different features are appropriate for breastfeeding.

The responses of the nursing mothers revealed that nursing mothers were able to identify the necessary features of an appropriate garment for breastfeeding. Such features are inconspicuous zippers at the princess lines at the centre front, a form of closure at the under bust using snaps and a form of closure using inconspicuous fastening at bust. Other features as identified by nursing mothers include flap covering fastening the layer of dress using snaps, concealed opening at invited pockets at bust regions and a form of closure using zipper in the centre front and side. These functional features of breastfeeding garment are mostly likely to make breastfeeding comfortable and fashionable for nursing mothers. In a similar study, Pooja and Gahlot (2016) have identified that maternity garments with functional features are very much required for lactating mothers and that there should be special maternity stores in each city. Also, Lamb and Kallal (1992) noted that useful features of nursing mother's garments include component of fit, insulation balance, ease-of-use, easy movement and its take-off

3.3. Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of young and old nursing mothers on challenges encountered in using the usual garments for breastfeeding.

Table 3: The t-test Analysis showing young and old nursing mothers on challenges encountered in using the usual garments for breastfeeding

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Young	257	19.94	6.645	353	-0.445	0.657	NS
Old	98	20.30	7.137				

Key: N = Number of respondents, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard deviation, df = degree of freedom

Source: *Field Survey (2019)*

The test of the hypothesis, as presented in Table 3, reveals mean responses of young and old nursing mothers as 19.94 and 20.30 respectively. The corresponding standard deviations are 6.645 and 7.137. The t-value of -0.445, at a degree of freedom of 353, shows no significant at a p-value of 0.657. Testing at an alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained since the p-value is greater than the alpha value. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of young and old nursing mothers on challenges encountered in using the usual garments for breastfeed.

Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that there is no significant difference between

the mean responses of young and old nursing mothers on challenges encountered in using the usual garments for breastfeeding. As against this finding, Shree (2016) opined that majority of first time mums are very secure about nursing their child in public. He further stated that they are bothered about unintentionally exposing their bodies and rely on bottle feeding when they are away from home. The research is limited to Ondo town because of lack of adequate fund for the researchers carry out the research in other parts of the country.

One implication of this research is that the results confirms that nursing mothers face different challenges when trying to breast feed in public and shows that nursing mothers can identify and will accept outfits that are comfortable for public breast feeding but these outfits are not accessible to them. The study identified the challenges of breast feeding mothers and features of suitable nursing garments that encourage breast feeding in public. Future studies might look into the mass production of suitable nursing garments and this study revealed that suitable nursing garments are not readily available and accessible.

4. Conclusion

The dawn of motherhood is accompanied with several challenges, which could be physiological or psychological. One of the prominent challenges of mother is breastfeeding. Nursing mothers are expected to breastfeed their babies exclusively for a particular period. In most cases, dress pattern changes during pregnancy and lactation, women are expected to wear clothes that allow easy access to breast milk by their babies. Traditional nursing dresses has posed several stress to nursing mothers including unavailability of the desired design for nursing garments, inappropriate time or place to express breastfeeding, inability to understand figure type and faults so as to choose suitable and flattering styles, inability to nursing garments that fit to the desired design as well as inability of a designer to sew. This category of people requires garments with functional features most especially garments with a form of closure using inconspicuous fastening at bust and garment with inconspicuous zippers at the princess lines at the centre front. These types or garment is discreet, convenient, comfortable and highly acceptable among nursing mothers. Based on the findings and the conclusion drawn of the study the following recommendations were made: Dress makers especially those within our locality should take a proactive stance and try to produce comfortable, convenient and beautiful designs for nursing mothers' garments for general acceptability. Nursing mothers should endeavour to take up the challenge of breastfeeding and be able to tackle it by wearing suitable garments for convenient breastfeeding. Dressmakers should improve knowledge to produce breastfeeding mothers' garments in different fitting styles suitable for all occasions.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby state that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: EOA & FDA

Data Curation: EOA & FDA

Data Analysis: EOA & FDA
Funding Acquisition: EOA & FDA
Investigation: EOA & FDA
Visualization: EOA & FDA
Resources: EOA & FDA
Writing original draft: EOA & FDA

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author

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